

MIRZO ULUG'BEK NOMIDAGI
O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETINING
JIZZAX FILIALI

**ZAMONAVIY INNOVATSION
TADQIQOTLARNING
DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI
VA RIVOJLANISH
TENDENSIYALARI:
YECHIMLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR
RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-TEXNIK
ANJUMAN MATERIALLARI
TO'PLAMI**

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**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI**

**MIRZO ULUG‘BEK NOMIDAGI O‘ZBEKISTON MILLIY
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MUAMMOLARI VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: YECHIMLAR
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tushintirilishi, anglab yetishiga ko‘mak berilishi mazmunan to‘g‘ri va maqbul ish bo‘lar edi.

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Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

1. Shoumarov G‘, Haydarov I, Sog‘inov N, Akramova F, Solihova G, Niyozmetova G. Oila psixologiyasi. Toshkent – “Sharq”, 2010. – 152 b. Shoumarov G‘, Haydarov I, Sog‘inov N, Akramova F, Solihova G, Niyozmetova G. Oila psixologiyasi. Toshkent – “Sharq”, 2010. – 152 b.

2. Common Causes of Family Conflict and How to Prevent Them. (Manba: <https://www.sterkfamilylaw.com/10-common-causes-of-family-conflict-and-how-to-prevent-them/>)

3. Мильшин А.О. Семья и семейные отношения. Цивилизационный взгляд /А.О. Мильшин. - Брянск: Ладомир, 2009. – 128 б.

4. Obozov N.N., Obozova A.N. Диагностика супружеских затруднений. Психологический журнал, Т.3, № 2, С.147-151, 2008. – 151 б.

5. Райгородский Д.Я. Диагностика семьи. Методики и тесты. Учебное пособие по психологии семейных отношений / под ред. Д.Я. Райгородского. – Самара: Издательский дом Бахрах-М, 2007. – 736 б.

6. Mahliyoхon Valijon qizi, M. Yosh oilalarda hissiy munosabatlarning ruhiy salomatlikka ta’siri, psixologik xususiyatlari. Qo‘qon DPI. Ilmiy Xabarlar Jurnal, 5(6-B), 38–43, 2025.

7. Yosh oila va unda yuzaga keladigan ziddiyatlar ijtimoiy-psixologik fenomen sifatida. In-Academy. (Manba: <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/22273>)

PSYCHOLOGY OF INTERNET ADDICTION AND PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Otamuratov Rustam Uskanovich

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan

Toshpulatov Nurmuhammad Shuhrat ogli

Student of group 423-22, psychology.

rustamota1989@gmail.com

Abstract. In this work, theoretical information about the general character traits of individuals prone to Internet addiction and the factors influencing it, as well as facts about the role of emotional intelligence in preventing Internet addiction, are provided.

Keywords: Internet, factor, social, concept, tendency, innovation, positive.

Аннотация. В данной работе представлена теоретическая информация об общих чертах характера людей, склонных к интернет-зависимости, и

факторах, влияющих на нее, а также факты о роли эмоционального интеллекта в предотвращении интернет-зависимости.

Ключевые слова: Интернет, фактор, социальный, концепция, тенденция, инновация, позитивный.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu ishimizda Internetga qaramlikka moyil bo'lgan shaxslarning umumiy xarakter tomonlari hamda unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar haqida nazariy ma'lumotlar hamda Internetga qaramlikning oldini olishda hissiy intellektning roli borasidagi haqiqatlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Internet, faktor, ijtimoiy, konsepsiya, moyillik, innovatsiya, pozitiv.

Introduction. Modern society is characterized by trends in the widespread use of the Internet. At the end of the last century (90s), a special socio-cultural environment was rapidly formed, characterized by the widespread use of all types of information resources and the limitlessness of their use [1]. The world is developing rapidly, and this also increases our enormous responsibility in protecting our youth from its various forms of dangers. After all, it is not surprising that these sentences uttered by the head of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev, also encourage young people to mature in the future, use their time effectively, and become competitive personnel. "The prospects of a nation and state whose children are educated, talented, confident in their own strength and potential, and who are always striving forward, will certainly be bright. We will continue to mobilize all our strength and capabilities to educate the youth of Uzbekistan as possessors of such noble qualities," his words also mobilize young people to work tirelessly on themselves, to look to the future with hope.

The availability of information in the virtual space of the Internet is associated with the beginning of a new stage in the development of mankind - the "cybernetic society", which is characterized by the increasing role of information resources as an engine of development [2]. In the modern world, the full spread of online services has become a necessity. The openness of information sources on the Internet and the increasing popularity of online services, the digitization of information, on the one hand, allow for the effective solution of various life tasks, and on the other hand, they lead to an increase in the time users spend on the Internet. In the field of psychology, the study of a person's relationships with other people in various areas has been carried out since the beginning of the 20th century. The initial interest in this issue was shown by representatives of symbolic interactionism and personology (W. James, C. Cooley, J. Mead).

We live in an era of increasing Internet addiction. In South Korea, it is considered one of the most serious health problems. The prevalence of Internet addiction among the population in the USA is 5%, in Europe it is from 2% to 4%, and in Asian countries the manifestation of Internet addiction is even more serious and covers 10.7% of users. According to various sources, the level of Internet addiction in Russia is from 1.7% to 4.3%. It is surprising that in a short time the Internet has firmly established itself in our lives and has caused a number of significant changes at the level of the human psyche, and this process continues. Against the background of the growth of Internet addiction, there are also

psychological mechanisms that affect it, and among these mechanisms it is worth highlighting emotional intelligence. World scientists have also conducted research on this issue, and I.N. Andreeva, R.Bar-On, A.G.Gladkikh, D.Goleman, S.P.Derevyanko, Yu.S.Dodonov, M.Seidner. Until now, the theoretical aspects of the study of emotional intelligence have been supplemented by empirical dissertation research, for example, among younger schoolchildren (K.S. Kuznetsova, 2012; A.E. Dobrin, 2015); in adolescence (Yu.V. Davydova, 2011); in adolescence and early adulthood (L. N Vakhrusheva, 2011); among university students (I.N. Meshcheryakova, 2011); in adults (T. S. Kiseleva, 2015). The role of emotional intelligence in improving the academic performance of secondary school students has been studied (F.Kh. Kobra, 2013) [3]. The work on the impact of Internet addiction on human psychology, and especially on the mental state of a person, is extremely relevant. According to the opinion of many scientists working on this problem (K. Yang, L.N. Yuryeva, Yu.A. Kleiberg, Yu.D. Babaeva, O.V. Smyslova, A.I. Mandel, A.Yu. Egorov, E.V. Zmanovskaya, etc.), Internet addiction is a behavioral disorder characterized by a compulsive desire to use the Internet and a computer (or a device that replaces it), regardless of the type of activity on the network, an involuntary desire to access the Internet in offline mode and the inability to leave the Internet during its use [4]. Neurobiological, genetic, social, psychological factors that cause the emergence of Internet addiction have been identified and extensive research has been conducted. However, one of the most relevant topics in the current context, "the importance of emotional intelligence in virtual environments," is a relatively understudied area. When we talk about "emotional intelligence," it is natural for the reader to ask, "What is emotional intelligence?" In order to eliminate this confusion, it is useful to present the definitions given by scientists to "Emotional Intelligence".

There has been a lot of debate about the definition of emotional intelligence among the above-mentioned and other scientists, but the scientists who have clearly thought in this area are Salovey and Mayer, who base emotional intelligence on 4 main aspects. These are:

1. Perception of feelings
2. Using emotions to think better
3. Understanding emotions
4. Managing emotions [5].

Psychologist Milford observed that students are increasingly using various social networks (e.g. blogs, forums, virtual communities) for various purposes, including entertainment, learning, and communication [6]. People's interest in the Internet has led to an increase in some factors and a decrease in some factors. Physiological factors, biological factors, and according to some scientists, genetic factors are also considered to be among the reasons for interest in the Internet.

Conclusion. The increase in Internet addiction can occur in a complex way depending on various factors. The emotional aspects of people prone to Internet addiction can be manifested as a prevention of addiction in them, and if the emotional states of people are developed in a regulatory way, the formation of addiction in them can be prevented. We have only studied this issue theoretically, but some related issues require

further research. For example, how do the cognitive aspects of people prone to Internet addiction develop? To what extent is this problem developed in older people? Therefore, we think it is important to continue research on this topic.

List of used literature

1. Андреева И.Н. Понятие и структура эмоционального интеллекта // Социально-психологические проблемы ментальности: 6-я Междунар. научно-практ. конф. 26-27 ноября 2004 г. Смоленск: В 2 ч. Ч. 1. Смоленск: Изд-во СГПУ, 2004. С. 22-26.
2. D. T. Shek and L. Yu, "Internet addiction phenomenon in early adolescents in Hong Kong", The Scientific World Journal, vol. 2012, Article ID 104304, 9 pages, 2012.
3. S. C. Milford, L. Vernon, J. J. Scott, and N. F. Johnson, "An initial investigation into parental perceptions surrounding the impact of mobile media use on child behavior and executive functioning", Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies, vol. 2022, pp. 1-11, 2022.
4. P. Salovey and J. D. Mayer, "Emotional intelligence," Imagination, Cognition and Personality, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 185-211.
5. Otamuratov R. U. Internet ijtimoiy tarmoqlari foydalanuvchilari faoliyatining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari bilan shaxsiy xususiyatlarning aloqasi //MedUnion. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 177-182.
6. Отамуратов Р., Отамуратова С., Розиккулова Д. Уникальность концепции эмоционального интеллекта в семейных отношениях //Информатика и инженерные технологии. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 423-428.

TAZIYIQ VA ZO‘RAVONLIKKA UCHRAGAN XOTIN-QIZLARGA IJTIMOIIY XIZMAT KO‘RSATISHNING HUQUQIIY VA PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI

Sattorova Mahliyo Burxanovna

Mirzo Ulug‘bek nomidagi O‘zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali
o‘qituvchisi

**Xudoyorova Sevinch Zarif qizi, Xo‘jaqulov Sardor Shuhrat o‘g‘li,
Mamadiyorov Sayfiddin Olim o‘g‘li**

Mirzo Ulug‘bek nomidagi O‘zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali
talabasi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda tazyiq va zo‘ravonlikka uchragan xotin-qizlarning ijtimoiy-psixologik holati, ularga ko‘rsatiladigan kompleks yordam (huquqiy, tibbiy, psixologik) mexanizmlari va rehabilitatsiya markazlarining o‘rni tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: tazyiq, zo‘ravonlik, ijtimoiy xizmat, rehabilitatsiya, himoya orderi, psixologik yordam, huquqiy hujjatlar.

Zo‘ravonlik – bu faqat shaxsiy muammo emas, bu jamiyat muammosi. Har bir ayol o‘zini xavfsiz his qilishi, hurmat va e‘tiborga loyiq. Psixologik yordam, huquqiy